

THE MATIC CLASSIFICATION OF FARSISM IN URDU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7388938>

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Abstract. *In India, many languages under the influence of Islamic culture, including Urdu, have a large number of Persian lexical borrowings that increase the reserve of literary language. During the acquisition process, a single feature such as the selectivity of the meanings of the borrowed lexicons is revealed. Words of Persian origin have come into contact with words of Sanskrit and Indian origin in Urdu, increasing its communicative effectiveness and removing the ambiguity of the original words. The semantic component of the vocabulary composition of the Persian language, which manifests itself in the lexical-semantic system and depends on it, has become important in solving the issue of adaptation of words of Persian origin to the Urdu language environment. The adoption of Persian lexemes in Urdu at the semantic level indicates both the regularity of borrowing and the existence of a historically justified need for it.*

Key words: Urdu, Persian, language, loanwords, lexicon, thematic classification

Аннотация. *В Индии многие языки под влиянием исламской культуры, в том числе и урду, имеют большое количество персидских лексических заимствований, увеличивающих резерв литературного языка. В процессе приобретения выявляется такая особенность, как избирательность значений заимствованных лексиконов. Слова персидского происхождения соприкоснулись со словами санскритского и индийского происхождения на урду, повысившего коммуникативную эффективность и устранив двусмысленность исходных слов. Семантическая составляющая словарного состава персидского языка, проявляющаяся в лексико-семантической системе и зависящая от нее, приобрела важное значение в решении вопроса адаптации слов персидского происхождения к языковой среде урду. Принятие персидских лексем в урду на*

семантическом уровне свидетельствует как о регулярности заимствования, так и о наличии в нем исторически обоснованной необходимости.

Ключевые слова: урду, персидский, язык, заимствования, лексика, тематическая классификация

The process of enrichment of the vocabulary of the Urdu language was closely related to the intensive state, economic, social, cultural, scientific development of the peoples of the Indian peninsula and the emergence of the Mughal Empire. During this period, there was a need for many new concepts and events related to various spheres of social, political and cultural life of the Indian subcontinent. The fact that the Persian language had a dominant position during the Mughal Empire created the foundation for the formation of certain thematic word groups of words of Persian origin in the Urdu language.

Words of Persian origin, which have been used in Urdu for centuries, attract attention with their strong lexical share and expressiveness. Words of Persian origin have strengthened their position in the Urdu language to such an extent that they have become natural lexical units of the Urdu language.

It should be taken into account that the units included in the dictionary of the language are arranged as soon as they are acquired. Spelling, explanatory and other dictionaries of each language serve to organize and organize the elements of the lexical system. In each language, the collected grouping of words is carried out specially. A thematic section of collected words after this problem. A number of thematic groups may be overlooked due to the distribution of collected materials.

It is important to group words of Persian origin in Urdu into different lexical-semantic groups. For example, the names of body parts, natural phenomena, words denoting geographical objects, kinship terms, household words, words on separate art fields, etc. The thematic division or lexical-semantic word groups of words that we will give differ from the previous ones both by the number of words included in them and by the new groups involved. At the same time, we should note that the thematic division of some of the words combined in separate art fields and terminological groups in this division did not exclude those words from being a separate object of analysis.

The word, which has gone through a long and complex development path, is always changing and enriching. If we pay attention to words of Persian origin in Urdu language, we will see that these words have complete, complete and also figurative meanings as a result of their full historical development. The words of Persian origin that passed into the Urdu language took an active part in the word creation of the

Urdu language, were used as the words of this language and caused certain changes in the process of historical development. Words of Persian origin cover many areas of social, political, economic, scientific and cultural life of Muslim Indians. If we look at the thematic classification of words of Persian origin in Urdu, we can see that most of these words are nouns and adjectives. Most of the borrowed words of Persian origin used in the lexicon of the Urdu language are single-meaning lexical units that express specific concepts and concepts. Most of such words appear in Urdu in their nominative sense. Words of Persian origin used in Urdu primarily consist of words and terms related to local conditions, lifestyle, customs and household. In the course of our research, we will try to describe the system relations of a number of lexical-semantic and thematic groups and to characterize the paradigm and characteristics of the syntagmatic relations of the Persian lexical units in these groups. According to the results of our analysis, lexical units of Persian origin in Urdu are divided into the following thematic groups: 1) Words expressing the concept of person; 2) Words expressing body parts; 3) Words expressing the concept of time; 4) Words denoting natural phenomena and geographical concepts; 5) Animal names; 6) Names of different plant groups; 7) Names of fruits and vegetables; 8) Jewelry and ornaments; 9) Clothing names; 10) Food and drink names; 11) Medical words; 12) Words related to the military field; 13) Words related to administrative, legal, socio-economic life; 14) Words denoting the names of places of residence, places and their parts; 15) Words expressing quality; 16) Words related to place of residence and place; 17) Words expressing abstract concepts; 18) Names of mythical beings; 19) Religious terms;

1. Words expressing the concept of person.

The words included in this semantic group can be divided into several subgroups:

a) words denoting art, profession, specialization:

The existence of assumptions that form a group of people characterized by their work, the nature of their activities and their related actions is related to the intensive state, economic, social, cultural and scientific development of nomads. In order for the local population to communicate in new realities, it was necessary to promote new participants of social relations. The words included in this group are specific nouns denoting the ownership of certain professions, arts and specialties. For example, استاد [ustad] – teacher; زرگر [zarqar] – jeweler; سوداگر [sodaqar] – trader; دیہگان [dihqān] – peasant; گواه [qavah] – witness; شاگرد [shaqird] – student; شیکاری [shikārī] – hunter; ماهی گیر [mahīqīr] – fisherman, etc.

b) words denoting custom, character, belief, abstract spiritual characteristics:

The words included in this subgroup mean people who have established any moral quality, character, and made themselves a profession. For example, نادان [nadan] – ignorant; فداکار [fadakar] – selfless; دروغ گو [duruğqu] – liar; گپ باز [qubāz] – gossip

c) words expressing the physical, physiological and mental states and conditions of a person.

The semantic content of words borrowed from the Persian language of the subgroup describing people characterized by their physical, physiological and mental states is determined not only by direct signs, but also by the individual's evaluation attitude. Thus, we can say that the meanings of this subgroup consist of lexical units resulting from different communication situations. For example, شادمان [şadman] – happy; تشنه [taşna] – thirsty; پشما [pişman] – regret; دیوانه [divana] – crazy; سرخوش [sarxoş] – drunk; مست [mast] – drunk; healthy etc.

Y.A. Rubinchik rightly noted in his book "Grammar of the Modern Persian Literary Language" that the biggest difficulties in the Persian language arise when defining the boundaries between parts of speech with noun groups. Farsi names cannot be assigned to one or another part of speech with absolute precision outside the (more simple) sentence. So, any image of it does not have specially expressed signs and can often express both the sign and its bearer¹.

As for the Urdu language, nouns formed as a result of the justification of derived adjectives of Persian origin in this subgroup occupy an important place as a sign of animation.

Lexemes denoting persons characterized by their physical, physiological and mental states are often found in the texts of artistic works, oral speech, as well as in aphorisms and proverbs: For example

d) words expressing relative names and social relations.

This sub-group includes words of Persian origin that denote persons with characteristic kinship and social relations with other people. For example, برادر [baradar] – brother; دختر [duxtar] – sister; یار [yar] – friend; دشمن [duşman] – enemy; دوست [dost] – dost; آشن [aşna] – acquainted; مهمان [mihman] – guest; بنده

¹Рубинчик Ю. А. Грамматика современного персидского литературного языка.–М. «Восточная литература» РАН, 2001. (p.99)

[banda] – person; خاوند[xavand] – husband; شوهر [şohar] – husband; داماد [damad] – son-in-law; خاله [xala] – aunt; فرزند [farzand] – son etc.

2. Words denoting body parts.

مو [mu] – hair; دست [dast] – hand; پا [pa] – foot; سر [sir] – head; انگشت [anqušt] – finger; دندان [dandan] – tooth; لب [lab] – lip; زبان [zaban] – tongue; دماغ [dimağ] – brain; پیشانی [pişani] – forehead; گوش [quş] – ear; چشم [çaşm] – eye; ابرو [abru] – eyebrow; شانه [şana] – shoulder; بناگوش [binaquş] – bottom of the ear; جگر [ciqar] – liver; ریش [reş] – beard; رخسار [ruxsar] – face; کلیحی [kalehi] – kidney; دوش [duş] – shoulder; بینی [bini] – nose; کف دست [kif dast] – palm; دهن [dahan] – mouth; پشت [pušt] – back; شکم [shikam] – abdomen; کمر [kamar] – waist; چهره [chuhra] – face; ناخن [naxun] – nail; دل [dil] – heart; پنجه [panca] – paw; آنسو [ansu] – tears; چشم [çaşm] – eye.

3. Words expressing the concept of time.

Words of Persian origin included in this group are mainly related to the organization of time in a person's life cycle. For example, همیشه [hameşa] – always; هرگز [harqiz] – never; هنوز [hanuz] – et etc.

4. Words denoting natural phenomena and geographical concepts.

هوا [hava] – wind; موسم [mousam] – season; آبشار [abşar] – waterfall; سیلاب [selāb] – flood; بارش [bariş] – rain; برف [baraf] – snow; آتش فشان [ataşfaşan] – volcano; کوه [kuh] – mountain; دریا [darya] – river etc.

5. Animal names.

The lexical-semantic group of loanwords with the general meaning of the names of fauna representatives in Urdu is represented by the following lexical units:

اسب [asp] – horse; مار [mar] – snake; شیر [şer] – lion; مرغا [murğa] – rooster; مرغی [murği] – hen; خرگوش [xarquş] – rabbit; بز [buz] – goat; گرگ [qurq] – wolf; سگ [saq] – dog; گربه [qurba] – cat; خرس [xars] – bear; آهو [ahu] – gazelle; پلنگ [palang] – tiger; موش [muş] – mouse; بندر [bandar] – monkey; ماهی [mahi] – fish; مگرمج [maqarmac] – crocodile; خروس [xurus] – rooster etc.

6. Names of different plant groups.

Lexical units of Persian origin included in the lexical-semantic group of names of various plant groups are represented by the following words in the dictionary of the Urdu language.

a) **tree names:** درخت [daraxt] – tree; شاخ [şax] – branch; چinar [çinar] – sycamore

b) **flower names:** گل [qul] – flower; نرگس [narqis] – daffodil; بنفشه [banofşa] – violet; یاسمین [yasmin] – jasmine; گلاب [qulab] – rose; سوسن [sosan] – iris; لاله [lala] – tulip.

7. Names of fruits and vegetables.

سبزی[sabzi] – vegetable; پیاز [piyaz] – onion; سیب [seb] – apple; کشمش [kişmiş] – raisin; بادام [badam] – almond; پسته [pusta] – pistachio; موز [muz] – banana; خرما [xurma] – dates; انگور [anqur] – grape; انار [anar] – pomegranate; خربوزه (خربزه) [xarbuza] – watermelon; انجیر [incir] – fig; آلوچه [aluça] – plum; چقندر [çukandar] – beetroot.

8. Jewelry and ornaments

بازوبند [bazuband] – bracelet; زنجیر [zancir] – chain; کمر بند [kamarband] – belt; کَمَر; گوشواره [quşvara] – earring etc.

9. Clothing names.

پرده [parda] – veil, niqab; رومال [romal] – towel; پاجامه [pacama] – pyjamas, trousers; شلوار [şalvar] – trousers; چادر [çadar] – cloak; پیراهن [pirahan] – shirt; چوغه [chugha] – chugha etc.

The names of different types of clothes of Persian origin used in Urdu mainly reflect important and archaic components of the material culture of Iranian-speaking peoples.

10. Food and drink names

The names of food and drink, which constitute one of the most important and most archaic components of the material culture of every nation, are also a major part of the lexical-semantic group in Urdu.

پنیر [panīr] – cheese; آب گوشت [abquşt] – soup; پلاؤ [pilao] – pilaf; شوربه [şorba] – soup; کباب [kabab] – kebab; نان [nan] – bread; آب [ab] – water; شراب [şarab] – wine.

11. Medical words.

بیمار [bimar] – sick; دوا [dava] – medicine; سوزن زنی [suzanzani] – needle stick; سردرد [sardard] – headache; خون کا فشار [xun ka fişar] – blood pressure; درد [dard] – pain

12. Names of household items and tools.

چارپائی [çarpayī] – bed; میز [mez] – table; قالین [kālīn] – carpet; [taba] – frying pan

13. Words related to the military field.

جنگ [canq] – war; لشکر [laşkar] – army; سرباز [sarbaz] – soldier; سپاہ [sipah] – soldier; گولہ [qula] – bullet; بروت [barut] – gunpowder.

14. Words related to administrative, legal, socio-economic life.

The lexical-semantic group of administrative words of Persian origin used in Urdu includes terms from the field of administrative management that ensures the functioning of state bodies and the judicial system. For example, شاه [şah] – king; بادشاه [badşah] – king; فرمان [farman] – ferman; وزیر [vazir] – minister; تاج [tac] – crown; تخت [taxt] – throne; مهر [muhr] – stamp; پایتخت [payetaxt] – capital.

Most of the words of Persian origin included in this group have become archaic words due to the loss of the facts describing the words in this lexical-semantic group and are mostly found in oral folk creations and classical literary examples.

15. Words denoting places of residence, places and their parts.

دیوان [zindan] – prison; سرائے [saraye] – palace; دروازہ [darvaza] – door; دیوار [divar] – wall; کتبخانہ [kutubxana] – library; غسل خانہ [guslxana] – bathroom; دواخانہ [davaxana] – pharmacy etc.

16. Words expressing quality.

خوب [xub] – good; خراب [xarab] – broken; بد [bad] – bad; گرم [qaram] – hot; سرد [sard] – cold; تاریک [tarik] – dark; روشن [roushan] – bright; نمکین [namken] – salty; دراز [daraz] – long; کوتاه [kutah] – short; پر [pur] – full; نرم [narm] – soft; سخت [saxt] – hard.

a) Colors.

سیاہ [siyah] – black; سفید [safed] – white; زرد [zard] – yellow; بنفشہ [banovşi] – purple, نارینجی [narinci] – orange; سبز [sabz] – green

17. Words expressing abstract concepts.

سوال [saval] – question; رفتار [raftar] – speed; آزادی [azadi] – freedom; راز [raz] – secret; تنہائی [tanhayi] – loneliness; خوبصورتی [xubsurati] – beauty

18. Names of mythical beings.

Words of Persian origin that form the lexical-semantic group of mythical beings in the modern Urdu language are represented by three concepts.

پری [pari] – fairy; دیو [div] – giant; اژدہا [ajdaha] – dragon.

19. Religious terms.

دین [din] – religion; جان [can] – soul; گناہ [qunah] – fault; پیغمبر [peiğambar] – prophet; خدا [xuda] – Allah; نماز [namaz] – namaz; روزہ [ruza] – fast; فردوس [firdus] – paradise

The words of this lexical-semantic group, which have undergone language adaptation over the centuries, have firmly entered the lexical composition of the Urdu language and are actively used both in the literary and artistic language, as well as in oral folk creativity.

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